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AVAILABILITY AND EXTENT OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY FACILITIES USAGE FOR SCHOOL RECORDS MANAGEMENT IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN IMO STATE

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Abstract

This study investigated availability and extent of Information and Communication Technology facilities usage for school records management in public secondary schools in Imo State. Two specific purposes, two research questions, and two hypotheses guided the study. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consisted of all the 314 principals in the 314 (134 urban and 180 rural) public secondary schools in Imo State. All the 314 (134 urban and 180 rural) public secondary school principals in Imo State were used for the study; thus, the census technique was adopted for the study. Researcher-structured rating scales titled “Availability of Information and Communication Technology Facilities Checklist (AICTFC) and Extent of Usage of Information and Communication Technology Facilities Rating Scale (EUICTRS) were used for data collection. The instruments were validated by three experts; two experts in the Department of Educational Management and Policy and one in Measurement and Evaluation Unit in the Department of Educational Foundations, all in the Faculty of Education Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. Internal consistency co-efficient of 0.91 and 0.89 was obtained for AICTFC and EUICTRS respectively using Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient. The researcher administered copies of the instruments to the respondents with the help of seven research assistants. Data were analyzed using frequencies, percentages, mean, standard deviation, chi-square, and independent t-test. The findings revealed that the state of ICT facilities in public secondary schools in Imo State is generally inadequate and significantly unavailable, with availability falling below the required standard in both urban and rural areas. The study also found among others that why ICT usage is relatively high in urban schools, rural schools demonstrate a low extent of utilization, highlighting a rural-urban disparity. Thus, the study concluded based on the findings that improving equitable ICT provision, especially in rural schools, is essential to enhance school records management, school administration, and bridge the

digital divide as well as promote effective educational service delivery. Based on the findings, the study recommended among others that the Imo State Ministry of Education, Secondary School Management Board, principals, and teachers should prioritize equitable provision, maintenance, and training for ICT facilities across urban and rural schools to enhance accessibility and balanced usage.

Key Words: Availability, Information and Communication Technology, Facilities, Records Management.

Introduction

Universally, education is regarded as one of the most important investments a country can make for her socio-economic and political transformation. This is premised on the ability of education to make individuals become proactive, secure firm control over their lives and widen their range of available options. In this regard, disparity in the development between developed and developing nations has been linked to education. This is perhaps why different countries accord recognition to education by investing heavily in this sub-sector. The United Nations Educational and Scientific Cultural Organization (UNESCO, 2024) considered education to be a basic human right and it is closely related to development in all segments; which includes social and human development. This position is amplified in the National Policy on Education (FRN, 2013) where it is explicitly stated that education shall continue to be highly rated in the national development plans because education is the most important instrument of change; any fundamental change in the intellectual and social outlook of any society has to be preceded by educational revolution. A comprehensive view into the Nigerian educational system shows that, education is systematically structured into pre-basic, basic, secondary and tertiary education.

Secondary school education refers to post-primary formal education offered to students who have successfully completed their primary school education. The secondary school education however, is not only designed to provide sound and responsible secondary school graduates for low level employment; but also to deposit in students quality education potentials to succeed in life upon graduation; if they cannot afford tertiary education. It is not surprising that Madudili (2022) maintained that secondary school education has always played an indispensable role in shaping the economic realities of any society. Secondary school education not only provides the youths with the opportunity to acquire the human capital that prepares them to pursue higher education in different areas of specialization, but it also improves their skills leading to higher labour productivity. This means that tertiary institutions and labour market depend largely on the qualified outputs from secondary schools for their inputs. Secondary education has continued to be important, and this is why there has been a growing concern about the quality of education that is offered in this level of education.

As a matter of fact, the attainment of the primary objectives of secondary education demands systematically collection, organization, and analysis of data to monitor student progress and academic performance, inform teaching strategies, allocate and utilize resources effectively to inform instructional planning, targeted interventions, and policy decisions through school records. According to Okeke and Eze (2021), school records are systematically collected, organized, and maintained data relating to students' academic performance, attendance, health, and behavior; which serve as a basis for decision-making and policy formulation in educational institutions. Ahmed and Musa (2023) described school records as documented information about all aspects of student life and school operations maintained systematically to support academic monitoring, resource allocation, and communication between stakeholders. Thus, proper documentation, accuracy, and accessibility of student and school information are essential to support decision-making, accountability, and effective educational planning through efficient school records management.

School record management is the planning, collection, organizing, storage, and keeping of schools' information or fact in such a way or manner that it can be retrieved when needed. According to Adewale and Bello (2020), school records management is the systematic control of the creation, maintenance, use, and disposition of educational records to ensure accurate documentation, legal compliance, and efficient decision-making in schools. Adewale and Bello further drew attention to systematic processes and linked school records to legal compliance and decision-making; which suggests that poor records management may expose schools to legal liabilities, hinder data-driven decisions, and affect educational planning. Nwankwo and Ugwuanyi (2022) viewed school records management as the coordinated activities of controlling educational data and documents throughout their lifecycle to support teaching, learning, administration, and future referencing. The effective records management ensures continuity and institutional memory, aids curriculum evaluation, and fosters effective communication, supports archival and research functions within the school system (Nwankwo and Ugwuanyi, 2022).

The goal of school records management is to ensure the accurate, secure, and systematic documentation of all academic and administrative activities for effective planning, accountability, and decision-making. It plays a vital role in creating an enabling teaching and learning environment by facilitating timely access to essential information that promotes transparency, continuity, improved students' outcomes and supporting efficient school operations. In secondary schools, the principal is a primary leader with an obligation of overseeing the attainment of laudable objectives of secondary school education as stipulated by the formulated policy on education. As a leader, the principal is crucial to improving teachers' job performance; he is vital to improvement of educational performance and eventual quality in the school. As a result, school principals have a responsibility of developing the vision that will guide the operations of their schools. It is the statement of vision, mission, and values defined by principals that will inspire quality oriented practices to support constant innovations, changes, improvement and proper

school records management and overall performance in schools. By virtue of their position, principals remain key figure in effective management of school records.

Regrettably, empirical evidence from research indicates persistent challenges with the leadership provided by principals in secondary schools across Nigeria. Various reports have highlighted concerns raised by stakeholders regarding the inadequacy and inefficiency of principals in managing school records effectively. This perceived leadership gap has been linked to declining quality in both educational inputs and outputs. Okeke and Eze (2021) observed that growing dissatisfaction around management and accountability in schools stems from the inability of principals to fulfill their administrative, instructional, and technical leadership roles. Likewise, Omodan et al. (2023) reported that many stakeholders associate the deteriorating standards in secondary education with the ineffective management of both statutory and non-statutory records by school principals. Adewale and Bello (2020) concluded that a core challenge facing the Nigerian educational system lies in the disorganization and mismanagement of schools' records; an issue that continues to hinder educational progress and development.

In today's era of globalization, principals can no longer afford to manage secondary school in ways that undermines quality. To remain competitive on a global scale, school leadership must prioritize quality assurance, continuous improvement, innovation, and effective school records management. Consequently, principals are required to adopt strategic management approaches that align with international educational standards and address the evolving demands of a knowledge-driven society. Achieving these objectives necessitates the implementation of proactive, visionary, and functional leadership practices within modern educational frameworks. Empirical studies have demonstrated that the integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) by school leaders significantly enhances school records management by ensuring accurate, efficient data handling, while simultaneously fostering the development of high-quality human capital through improved access to information and learning resources.

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) refers to a comprehensive suite of technologies designed to facilitate the management, processing, and dissemination of information. It encompasses a wide range of tools, including hardware, software, and network systems, that support the acquisition, storage, retrieval, and sharing of data. Federal Ministry of Education (FME, 2020) remarked that ICT integrates computing devices, networking, and digital communication systems to promote efficient data exchange, collaboration, and decision-making. Within the ICT domain, two core components emerge: Information Technology (IT); which involves the use of electronic systems for data storage and management, and Communication Technology; which focuses on the transmission and interpretation of information through digital platforms such as email, messaging applications, video conferencing, and network-based communication tools. Agada and Eze (2024) defined ICT as a suite of digital tools and applications that streamline data generation, modification, and transmission. Oluleye, Issa, and Bello (2024)

similarly described ICT as a convergence of telecommunications, computing, and multimedia technologies that facilitate the seamless flow of information. Oladokun, Seidu, Ogunbiyi, Aboyade, Yemi-Peters and Elai (2022) emphasized that ICT has the transformational power of reshaping societal functions, enhancing global connectivity, promoting digital commerce, and enabling innovative educational environments.

Drawing from this synthesis, ICT can be understood as encompassing a broad range of technologies including computer hardware, broadcast systems, online databases, CD-ROMs, and emerging innovations such as robotics, digital television, and videoconferencing. This all-encompassing framework merges traditional IT infrastructure with modern communication technologies to create dynamic and integrated information systems (Nnaji and Unamba, 2025). With respect to secondary school education, ICT plays a vital role in the management of school records. It serves as a strategic enabler, which supports data-driven decision-making and enhancing administrative efficiency. ICT facilitates real-time access to student records, attendance logs, performance reports, and other school documents; thus streamlining the responsibilities of school principals in records management. Furthermore, ICT promotes a more learner-centered approach by shifting the educational focus from teacher-led instruction to interactive and exploratory learning (Falebita, 2022).

ICT enhances the quality of instruction and empowers students to independently acquire and apply knowledge, as well as transforming educators into facilitators and mentors. According to the National Open University of Nigeria (as cited in Asiegbu and Ezema, 2024), common ICT tools in school administration include computers, internet connectivity, projectors, Learning Management Systems (LMS), interactive whiteboards, audiovisual aids, tablets, cloud storage, and virtual conferencing tools. These technologies have revolutionized educational management, making administrative tasks more transparent, accessible, and efficient. Nonetheless, a digital divide exists globally, where nations are classified as developed, developing, or underdeveloped based on their access to ICT infrastructure. While technologically advanced countries experience improved educational outcomes and institutional efficiency, others face significant barriers to ICT integration.

A substantial body of literature supports the view that the integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) facilities plays a pivotal role in achieving effective school records management. Empirical evidence supports the assertion that the availability and strategic utilization of ICT facilities in urban and rural areas by principals are critical determinants of efficient school records management in secondary schools. Conversely, the absence or underutilization of such facilities significantly hampers administrative effectiveness; consequently depriving schools of essential tools for accurate, timely, and organized record keeping. In line with this perspective, Akinyemi and Okeke (2021) contended that failure of educational institutions to implement ICT resources poses a significant challenge to effective school records management, warning that such

institutions risk descending into administrative redundancy and inefficiency. These insights stress the necessity of ICT-driven records management systems for sustaining institutional relevance and enhancing decision-making processes within the educational sector. Prompted by these observations, the researcher was motivated to systematically investigate the availability and extent of ICT facilities usage for school records management in public secondary schools in Imo State.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The management of school records in secondary schools is expected to be efficient, accurate, and timely to support informed decision-making, accountability, and strategic planning. This expectation presupposes the availability and optimal usage of modern Information and Communication Technology (ICT) facilities such as desktop computers, laptops, cloud-based storage servers, database management systems, internet connectivity, specialized software, and electronic storage systems. With these tools in place, school records such as students' academic performance, staff records, attendance, health data, and financial documents can be securely stored, easily retrieved, and effectively monitored. The integration of ICT in records management should minimize human error, reduce paperwork, prevent data loss, and enhance data security; thus improving the overall administrative effectiveness of public secondary schools in Imo State.

However, contrary to this expectation, school records management in many secondary schools in Imo State is still characterized by manual processes that are time-consuming, prone to errors, and vulnerable to damage or loss. From the researcher's practical experience and observation, it appears that the availability of ICT facilities in these schools is limited. Even in schools where ICT tools exist, there is often minimal or ineffective usage due to poor maintenance, lack of training, irregular power supply, or resistance to change. This disconnects between the potentials of ICT and its actual deployment in records management undermines administrative efficiency, data accuracy, and timely decision-making; hence raising serious concerns about the quality of data available for planning and monitoring of educational activities. If urgent measures are not taken to enhance the availability and effective usage of ICT facilities for school records management, schools risk facing persistent challenges in information retrieval, transparency, accountability, and planning. Over time, this could undermine the efficiency of the educational system, compromise data security, delay policy implementation, and hinder national and state-level educational reforms. These concerns however raised the following questions: are ICT facilities adequately available in secondary schools in Imo State for effective schools record management? To what extent are the available ICT facilities in secondary schools in Imo State being utilized for school records management? Hence, the problem of this study was to investigate availability and extent of Information and Communications Technology facilities usage for school records management in public secondary schools in Imo State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to investigate availability and extent of Information and Communication Technology facilities usage for school records management in public secondary schools in Imo State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. ascertain the available ICT facilities for school records management in public secondary schools in Imo State.
2. examine the extent of ICT facilities usage for school records management in public secondary schools in Imo State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. Are ICT facilities available for school
2. To what extent are ICT facilities used for school records management in public secondary schools in Imo State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses formulated for the study were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. Urban and rural school principals do not differ significantly in their responses on the availability of ICT facilities for school records management in public secondary schools in Imo State.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean scores of urban and rural school principals on the usage of ICT facilities for school records management in public secondary schools in Imo State.

Method

The descriptive survey research design was employed for this study. The study was conducted in Imo State, Nigeria. The population of the study comprised all the 314 principals in the 314 public secondary schools in Imo State. All the 314 (134 urban and 180 rural) public secondary school principals in Imo State were used for the study. Structured questionnaires titled: Availability of Information and Communication Technology Facilities Checklist (AICTFC) and Extent of Usage of Information and Communication Technology Facilities Rating Scale (EUICTRS). The instruments were validated by three experts in Faculty of Education Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. Internal consistency co-efficient of 0.91 and 0.89 were obtained for AICTFC and EUICTRS using Cronbach's Alpha method. The researchers administered the instrument to the respondents with the help of five trained research assistants. Out of the 314 copies administered, 302 copies were retrieved properly completed, and used for data analysis. This gave a return rate of 96.18%, which the researcher considered adequate for the study. Simple frequencies and percentages were used to answer research questions one. A score

of 50% was taken as benchmark for accepting an item as Available, while a score below 50% was regarded as Not Available while aggregate mean and standard deviation were employed in answering research question four. A criterion mean of 2.50 was used in accepting an item as Agree. Chi-square statistics was used in testing hypotheses one while t-test analysis was used for testing hypotheses two. A null hypothesis was rejected where the calculated p-value is less than the stipulated level of significance (0.05). The reverse was the case where the calculated p-value is greater than the stipulated level of significance.

Results

Table 1: Availability of Information and Communication Technology Facilities

S/N	ICT Facilities (N = 302)	Available		Not Available		Remark
		F	%	F	%	
1.	Desktop Computers	134	44.4	168	55.6	Not Available
2.	Laptop Computers	129	42.7	173	57.3	Not Available
3.	Printers	118	39.1	184	60.9	Not Available
4.	Photocopiers	121	40.1	181	59.9	Not Available
5.	Scanners	127	42.1	175	57.9	Not Available
6.	External Hard Drives	138	45.7	164	54.3	Not Available
7.	Flash Drives (USB Drives)	142	47.0	160	53.0	Not Available
8.	Uninterruptible Power Supply	135	44.7	167	55.3	Not Available
9.	Smartphones	184	60.9	118	39.1	Available
10.	CCTV Systems	97	32.1	205	67.9	Not Available
11	Student Information Mgt. Systems	72	23.8	230	76.2	Not Available
12	Spreadsheet Software	142	47.0	160	53.0	Not Available
13	Word Processing Software	130	43.0	172	57.0	Not Available
14	Cloud Storage Services	106	35.1	196	64.9	Not Available
15	Email Services	193	63.9	109	36.1	Available
16	Time-Stamping Software	118	39.1	184	60.9	Not Available
17	Internet Access	130	43.0	172	57.0	Not Available
18	Local Area Network (LAN)	148	49.0	154	51.0	Not Available
19	Online Result Portal	190	62.9	112	37.1	Available
20	Biometric Attendance System	118	39.1	184	60.9	Not Available
	Aggregate	134	44.4	168	55.6	Not Available

Table one shows the frequencies and percentage responses on available ICT facilities for school records management in public secondary schools in Imo State. The results indicate that three (smartphones, Email services, and online results portal) out of the twenty enumerated ICT facilities are available for school records management. The remaining seventeen ICT facilities however, are not available as demonstrated by over 50% (55.6%) of the principals. They include: desktop computers, laptop computers, printers,

photocopiers, scanners, flash drives, external hard drives, CCTV systems, Biometric Attendance System, internet access, cloud storage systems, among other listed ICT facilities.

Table 2: Mean ratings of the extent of ICT facilities used for school records management in public secondary schools in Imo State

S/N	As a principal, I use:	Schools = 302		
		\bar{X}	SD	Remarks
1	desktop computers for processing students' academic records.	2.45	1.38	Low Extent
2	laptop computers for easy accessing of records remotely.	2.49	1.35	Low Extent
3	printers for printing students' academic records for easy documentation.	2.46	1.34	Low Extent
4	photocopiers for duplicating students' academic files.	2.46	1.31	Low Extent
5	scanners for converting paper records into digital form.	2.44	1.32	Low Extent
6	external hard drives for backing up school records securely.	2.47	1.37	Low Extent
7	flash drives for transferring school records between systems.	2.27	1.37	Low Extent
8	Uninterruptible Power Supply (UPS) for preventing data loss during power failure.	2.49	1.32	Low Extent
9	smartphones for communicating students' data on-the-go.	2.49	1.29	Low Extent
10	CCTV Systems for monitoring physical security of records rooms.	2.41	1.37	Low Extent
11	Student Information Systems for managing students' personal data.	2.45	1.38	Low Extent
12	spreadsheet software for recording analyzed student scores.	2.51	1.36	High Extent
13	word-processing software for creating students' documents.	2.47	1.34	Low Extent
14	cloud storage services for storing records online.	2.47	1.31	Low Extent
15	Email services for communicating student-related documents.	2.42	1.32	Low Extent
16	timetabling software for organizing class records.	2.46	1.38	Low Extent
17	internet access for connecting to online record platforms.	2.31	1.38	Low Extent
18	Local Area Network for sharing records within the school system.	2.51	1.32	High Extent
19	online result portal for publishing students' results online.	2.41	1.29	Low Extent
20	biometric attendance system for recording students' daily attendance.	2.33	1.37	Low Extent
Aggregate		2.44	1.34	Low Extent

Table 2 shows the mean and standard deviation scores on the extent of ICT facilities usage for school records management in public secondary schools in Imo State. The results indicate that the aggregate mean score of principals on the extent of ICT facilities usage is 2.44 with corresponding standard deviations of 1.34. This implies that principals in public secondary schools in Imo State agreed that the highlighted ICT facilities are not fully utilized for records management in their schools. Consequently, the standard deviation of 1.34 indicates moderate variability in responses, suggesting a heterogeneous opinion among the principals.

Table three: Summary of the Chi-Square analysis on principals’ responses on the availability of ICT facilities for school records management in public secondary schools in Imo State

Source of Variation	N (302)	Df	α	χ^2 Cal	χ^2 Crit.	P-value	Remark
Urban Schools Available	(N=133) 58 (43.6)	1	0.05	24.251 ^a	21.671	0.001	Significant
Urban Schools Not Available	75 (56.4)						
Rural Schools Available	(N=169) 35 (20.7)						
Rural Schools Not Available	134 (78.3)						

The chi-square test analysis in Table Two showed that $X^2 (1, N = 302) = 24.251$, and the P-value = $0.001 < 0.05$ significant level. The null hypothesis was not upheld while the alternative hypothesis was upheld; thus, urban and rural school principals differ significantly in their responses on the availability of ICT facilities for school records management in public secondary schools in Imo State.

Table 4: Summary of the Chi-Square analysis on urban and rural school principals on the usage of ICT facilities for school records management in public secondary schools in Imo State

Variable	N	\bar{X}	SD	df	t	Sig. (2-tailed)	Decision
Urban	133	1.92	1.15862	300	-7.048	.000	Sig.
Rural	169	2.84	1.10599				

The results in Table Eight indicate the summary of the t-test analysis on urban and rural school principals on the usage of ICT facilities for school records management in public secondary schools in Imo State. The results reveal that the calculated independent t-test was -7.048 with a p-value of 0.00. Based on this, the null hypothesis was not retained and the alternative hypothesis was retained. Thus, there is significant difference in the mean scores of urban and rural school principals on the usage of ICT facilities for school records management in public secondary schools in Imo State. This implies that the availability of ICT facilities in rural areas differs from urban areas for school records management.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study revealed that ICT facilities are largely unavailable for records management in public secondary schools in Imo State, as indicated by an aggregate percentage of 55.6%. This suggests that more than half of the essential ICT tools such as computers, scanners, projectors, internet connectivity, database management systems, and relevant software are not adequately provided or accessible for effective school records management. The unavailability of these facilities poses significant challenges to efficient documentation, storage, retrieval, and security of academic and administrative records, which are crucial for transparency, accountability, and informed decision-making in schools. The result highlights infrastructural and resource gaps that may be attributed to factors such as insufficient government funding, poor prioritization of ICT integration in education, lack of maintenance culture, and inadequate partnerships with private organizations for ICT provision. Furthermore, the absence of ICT facilities could hamper the adoption of digital record management systems thereby compelling schools to rely heavily on manual processes; which are often slow, prone to errors, and susceptible to loss or damage of records. This emphasizes the urgent need for targeted policies and interventions aimed at equipping schools with the necessary ICT infrastructure to enhance administrative efficiency and support educational development in the State.

The finding of this study also showed that ICT facilities are utilized at a low extent for school records management in public secondary schools in Imo State, with an aggregate mean of 2.44 and a standard deviation of 1.34. This low mean, based on a 4-point rating scale, falls below the acceptable threshold of 2.50; thus, indicating that the integration of ICT in managing records such as student bio data, staff records, attendance logs, academic results, and financial records is still minimal. The relatively high standard deviation of 1.34 further suggests inconsistency in the responses, pointing to disparities among schools some mostly in urban areas possibly using ICT tools marginally, while others mainly in rural schools are still relying heavily on manual, paper-based methods. Contributing factors may include limited ICT infrastructure, lack of capacity building for staff, unreliable electricity supply, inadequate internet connectivity, and insufficient government funding. Table Eight complements this by establishing a statistically significant difference in ICT usage between urban and rural school principals with a t-test value of -7.048 and a p-value of 0.000 at a 0.05 level of significance. The negative t-value indicates that urban schools have a higher mean usage of ICT than rural schools. This urban-rural digital divide could stem from better access to technology, improved infrastructure, and increased exposure to digital literacy initiatives in urban areas, while rural areas continue to grapple with infrastructural challenges and poor ICT policy implementation.

In agreement with this study's findings, Edeh et al. (2021) conducted a study in southeastern Nigeria and found that ICT usage for educational administration, especially in rural secondary schools, was significantly low due to infrastructural decay and inadequate ICT training for staff. Their study reported that over 70% of rural school

administrators relied on manual record-keeping systems, confirming a widespread deficiency in digital adoption. Correspondingly, Edeh, Okonkwo and Chikaodili (2023) reported that the use of ICT for records management was significantly more prevalent in urban public secondary schools compared to rural ones in Anambra and Imo States, with urban schools benefiting from better funding, government projects, and non-governmental digital literacy campaigns. In contrast, a study by Olowu and Olayemi (2022) in Lagos State found no significant difference in ICT usage between urban and rural public secondary schools, with both zones demonstrating moderate to high levels of ICT integration for records management. The divergence in findings could be attributed to regional disparities; Lagos, being a more technologically advanced and economically privileged state, may have implemented more robust ICT policies and infrastructure even in its rural areas, unlike Imo State where rural schools still face systemic barriers to ICT integration. Thus, while the present study aligns with existing literature on rural ICT deficiencies, contextual factors such as regional development, policy priorities, and administrative support explain variations across these states in Nigeria.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the researchers concluded that improving equitable ICT provision, is essential to enhance school records management, school administration, and bridge the digital divide as well as promote effective educational service delivery.

Recommendations

- Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:
1. Imo State Ministry of Education should prioritize equitable provision of modern ICT facilities across urban and rural public secondary schools and implement policies that promote their optimal integration into teaching, learning, and records management.
 2. Secondary School Management Board should develop and enforce standardized ICT usage guidelines while ensuring regular monitoring, maintenance, and equitable distribution of ICT resources to bridge the rural-urban disparity.
 3. Principals in secondary schools in Imo State should actively foster an ICT-friendly school culture by encouraging teachers and students to integrate available facilities into daily academic activities and records management practices.
 4. Teachers should engage in continuous professional development on ICT integration and creatively adapt available resources to enhance instructional delivery and students' learning experiences.

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